

Data Management Plan for "From Whispering Gallery Mode Doped Microspheres to Photonic Integrated Circuits for Advanced Next-Generation Applications"

Version 2

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) covers the data that will be collected while implementing the project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/190 "From Whispering Gallery Mode Doped Microspheres to Photonic Integrated Circuits for Advanced Next-Generation Applications" (hereinafter referred to as the Project). The aim of the Project is to investigate doped whispering gallery mode microspheres and tantalum pentoxide photonic integrated circuits' potential for lasing, optical frequency comb generation, and other advanced photonic applications. Planned research outputs of the Project are experiment raw data, experiment metadata, analysed data, deliverable data reports. All research data collected as part of the Project is owned by the University of Latvia. The project leader of the Project will take responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data.

The aim and purpose of the DMP is to detail and guarantee the preservation of the data and documents collected during the Project, as well as any results derived from it. Proper data management - recording of collected data, storage and dissemination of the results - is important to ensure data collected for the Project is safely secured over its life cycle. The DMP includes multiple ways to responsibly manage the data.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

From Whispering Gallery Mode
Doped Microspheres to
Photonic Integrated Circuits for
Advanced Next-Generation
Applications
(1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/190)

Researchers

Inga Brice (0000-0002-5560-6574)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for "From Whispering Gallery Mode Doped Microspheres to Photonic Integrated Circuits for Advanced Next-Generation Applications"](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) covers the data that will be collected while implementing the project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/190 "From Whispering Gallery Mode Doped Microspheres to Photonic Integrated Circuits for Advanced Next-Generation Applications" (hereinafter referred to as the Project). The aim of the Project is to investigate doped whispering gallery mode microspheres and tantalum pentoxide photonic integrated circuits' potential for lasing, optical frequency comb generation, and other advanced photonic applications. Planned research outputs of the Project are experiment raw data, experiment metadata, analysed data, deliverable data reports. All research data collected as part of the Project is owned by the University of Latvia. The project leader of the Project will take responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data.

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Researchers:

[Inga Brice \(0000-0002-5560-6574\)](#)

Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [From Whispering Gallery Mode Doped Microspheres to Photonic Integrated Circuits for Advanced Next-Generation Applications \(1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/190\)](#)

Data Management Plan | Data Management Plan for "From Whispering Gallery Mode Doped Microspheres to Photonic Integrated Circuits for Advanced Next-Generation Applications" LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 07/04/2026

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-31](#)

4. Templates

[Descriptions](#)

[Experiment Data](#)

This section describes the raw experimental data generated during the Project to support the analysis of optical quality and its relationship to fabrication and preparation procedures. Recoded datasets will enable a feedback loop for optimization and informed selection of samples for further application testing.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The Project will generate data. The data, samples, and materials expected to be produced will consist of raw data files from experiments, experiment and method notes, experimental The Project will generate experimental data to support the analysis and optimization of samples for fabrication of doped microspheres and characterization of tantalum pentoxide photonic integrated circuits for photonic

applications. The data will be used to establish a feedback loop between optical quality measurements, fabrication methods, and preparation procedures, enabling the identification of process parameters that lead to optimal performance. This feedback will guide the selection of the most suitable samples for subsequent application testing. analysis data files, microscopy images, photos and videos.

Raw data files will consist of ASCII text directly collected from photo-detectors during measurements of transmission signal and calibration signal used for assessing the quality of the samples. Screenshots, photos (including microscopy images) and videos will be part of the raw data collection. Experiment notes will describe the experiments and methods, including details like, sample coating materials, concentrations, fabrication and preparation procedures, experimental environment and parameters. Additionally, any observations, procedures, and ideas generated during the course of the experiment will be recorded. Read me notes will be created as soon as the data is collected or produced, thus allowing efficient management. Experimental analysis data files will consist of spreadsheets and plots of the raw data that have been manipulated to yield meaningful and quantitative information and values for assessment of the microresonator quality and applications. The analysis will be performed using best practice and acceptable methods for calculating quality factors and determining more suitable sample preparation procedures.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- ODT

- ODS
- PNG
- JPG
- Others

MP4, QTI, OPJ, ODG, SVG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No. The Project will generate new experimental data specifically needed for implementing the research objectives. Re-use of existing datasets was not considered, as the Project requires the generation of new experimental data under specifically designed fabrication and preparation conditions. The data must be directly linked to sample optical quality assessment to enable the intended feedback loop and reliable evaluation selection of samples for application testing.

The only exception is the limited re-use of previously obtained data generated during the development of the fabrication method and erbium-ion doping of silica microspheres (project No. LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0009 "Development of optoplasmonic doped whispering gallery mode resonator"), which will be used for methodological reference and comparison.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data generated during the Project will be primarily useful to the project leader for analysing the relationship between fabrication procedures, chosen dopants, resulting optical quality, and potential applications. More broadly, the data may be of interest to researchers and engineers working with optical materials, and optical characterization, as it could support method development, process optimization, and comparative studies.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

The Project will generate a large volume of data, some of which may not be appropriate for sharing since it may involve data quality issues like “missing data”, “incorrect data”, “irrelevant data” etc. To ensure data quality control, calibration data will be recorded, data capture protocols will be developed, and multiple samples will be fabricated for measurements. Publicly available data will be included in scientific journal publication, where it will undergo peer review. Preferably, results obtained from the raw data will be published in peer-reviewed open source publications. Researchers will be able to access published data using DataverseLV or Zenodo repository.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Access to the data will be restricted during the active phase of the Project and until the results have undergone peer review and been published. This embargo is necessary to ensure data quality control, proper interpretation of results, and the protection of publication priority and potential intellectual property.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

DataverseLV is Latvia’s national research data repository, operated in line with national open science and research data management policies. Using it ensures compliance with Latvian funding and institutional requirements.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The experimental data generated during the Project will be stored in standard, widely used formats whenever possible, ensuring compatibility with common data analysis software. Accessing and analysing the data will require standard software tools for data visualization. Data produced during analysis using specialized programs, such as QtiPlot or Origin, will not be publicly shared, only the processed or raw data in standard formats will be made available.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The raw data will be stored in open or widely used interoperable formats (txt, pdf, png, mp4), which can be accessed by multiple software applications and operating systems. Data files will be accompanied by read me file (txt) describing measurement conditions, fabrication parameters, units, and sample identifiers, enabling comparison and integration with related datasets.

Software-specific analysis files may be generated during data analysis but these files will not be publicly shared. Only the raw data in interoperable formats will be made available.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes. Selected datasets generated within the Project will be made available for reuse by third parties after the end of the project. These datasets will be published in the repository following peer-reviewed publication of results. This data will be accompanied by sufficient notes to support understanding and reuse.

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2039-01-01

Data will be preserved for long-term (minimum of 10 years after publication) re-use in accordance with repository and institutional retention policies.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs related to making the data FAIR, including open source publication, are covered by the Project budget. No additional resources are needed for data management and storage, as DataverseLV and Zenodo repositories are free of charge.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Inga Brice (0000-0002-5560-6574)

The project leader is solely responsible for all data management activities, including data collection, documentation, storage, quality control, data analysis and preparation of datasets for re-use.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Storage and backup will be ensured for the duration of the Project by the project leader. All data will be stored on the project leaders personal work computer (protected with password) hard drive and dubbed in OneDrive cloud storage (protected with 2FA) linked with the work e-mail provided by the University of Latvia. This includes all data levels: raw data, notes, analysed data.

OneDrive file storage offers high-level data preservation, security and accessibility by automatic syncing, back up, multiple version storing, and selective data sharing options. Chosen storage option will mitigate data loss and data corruption risk. Relevant data and publication drafts will be shared with co-investigators, and partners. Only authorized members will have access to the storage.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Deliverables

This section describes project deliverables in the form of reports, instructions, know-how, methodologies, prototype descriptions, etc. These outputs documents developed during the implementation of the Project will form the main intellectual property and support reproducibility, transfer of knowledge, and sustainability.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The Project will generate experimental data to support the analysis and optimization of samples for fabrication of doped microspheres and characterization of tantalum pentoxide photonic integrated circuits for photonic applications. The data will be compiled into written deliverable reports. Deliverables will be portable document files containing analysed and visualized data derived from raw data and other project activities.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- ODT
- PNG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No. The deliverables will be generated directly from experimental datasets produced within the Project and described in previous section.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

No. The deliverables will include an appropriate level of detail and context, such as methods, instructions, and descriptions, ensuring that the information is interpretable and usable without the need for additional files.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Restricted access is necessary to protect proprietary knowledge, ensure appropriate use, and preserve potential for commercialization or further research.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Only raw experimental data and peer-reviewed publications will be made accessible for public.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Instructional material and relevant technical reports will be provided as written documents (OpenDocument files *.odt and Microsoft office *.docx editable for personal use), presentations/posters (OpenDocument files *.odp and Microsoft office *.pptx editable for personal use), LaTeX files (*.tex, *.bib, *.sty, etc.) together

with image files (editable OpenDocument images *.odg exported as *.png, *.svg or *.pdf). Final versions of deliverables will be converted to PDF format for better compatibility.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Final versions of deliverables will be converted to PDF format for better compatibility.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Other (Not Open)

The re-use of deliverables will be restricted due to the intellectual property rights and potential possibility to commercialize and license them in the future.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

The re-use of deliverables will be restricted due to the intellectual property rights and potential possibility to commercialize and license them in the future.

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The re-use of deliverables will be restricted due to the intellectual property rights and potential possibility to commercialize and license them in the future.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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The project leader is solely responsible for all data management activities, including generating deliverables and protecting intellectual property access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Storage and backup will be ensured for the duration of the Project by the project leader. All data will be stored on the project leaders personal work computer (protected with password) hard drive and dubbed in OneDrive cloud storage (protected with 2FA) linked with the work e-mail provided by the University of Latvia. This includes all data levels: raw data, notes, analysed data. OneDrive file storage offers high-level data preservation, security and accessibility by automatic syncing, back up, multiple version storing, and selective data sharing options. Chosen storage option will mitigate data loss and data corruption risk. Relevant data and publication drafts will be shared with co-investigators, and partners. Only authorized members will have access to the storage.

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